

ADVANTAGES OF THE METHODOLOGY OF USING MULTIMEDIA

Rakhimov Sabir Ziyadullaevich

Associate professor

Department of Mathematics and Informatics

Uzbekistan-Finland Pedagogical Institute

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Abstract. *The article talks about the creation of multimedia didactic tools for non-specialized educational areas of higher educational institutions and the development of scientifically based methodological recommendations for lectures and practical classes with their use. Also, on the basis of the created multimedia didactic tools, the methods of pedagogical analysis, the development and application of the method of organizing test work, as well as methods for determining their effectiveness in the experiment are covered in detail.*

Keywords: *multimedia, didactic tool, quality of education, electronic textbook, information technology.*

Improving the pedagogical requirements for the structure and content of multimedia didactic tools, the criteria and stages of creation by analyzing the work in the direction of creating multimedia didactic tools from information technologies created for the education system of our country and abroad, and their introduction into education, remains an issue of the agenda today. One of the main tasks of pedagogues-experts is to determine the basics and principles of the technology of creating and using modern didactic tools for teaching non-specialist students of higher educational institutions, their general structure and specific characteristics.

In recent years, higher educational institutions have been clarifying the pedagogical possibilities of using multimedia tools in the educational process based on the methods of information transfer and didactic problem solving through media tools, and the content of the pedagogical goals of its use. The content of psychological and pedagogical requirements for the creation of a multimedia textbook is being improved based on the inclusion of didactic tools with interactive criteria (teaching cooperation, knowledge base, feedback) with a motivational effect. It is appropriate if the stages of pedagogical design of electronic textbooks include structural classification of multimedia tools (according to functional purpose, according to teaching tools and systems) and categorization according to pedagogical activities (linear, hypertext, manual, creation).

In the article, we will briefly talk about the method of using the electronic software tool and the multimedia electronic textbook for the scientific and methodological support of the science "Information Technologies in Education" for the non-specialist educational directions of the higher education institutions.

Currently, a sufficient number of new information technology tools have been developed and are being used. Their number changes every year. The following can be included in their list: display, printer, memory, computer sound input device, scanner, keyboard, data store, knowledge store, multimedia systems, videotext, teletext, TV news, modem, computer networks, e-mail, electronic conferencing, information retrieval systems, digital cameras, expert training systems, graphic information output device, hypertext systems, television, radio, telephone, fax, voice e-mail, teleconferencing, electronic whiteboard, software tools on the Internet, automated libraries,

software tools for teaching, editorial-publishing systems, software packages (programming languages, translators), data transmission tools, radio stations, etc. Development of methods of introduction of multimedia technologies in the educational process, improvement of computer literacy of students studying in non-specialist education is considered an urgent problem. Therefore, studying the problems of the technology of creating electronic educational literature and applying them to the teaching process is one of the ways to increase the effectiveness of the educational process.

Multimedia is a multi-component environment that provides the use of text, graphics, video and animation in the communication mode and expands the possibilities of using the computer in the educational process. Creative thinking helps learners to take the material presented holistically. There will be an opportunity to combine theoretical and demonstration materials.

The pedagogical goals of using new information technology tools are as follows:

- acceleration of all stages of the educational process in the classroom;
- development of all-round knowledge of the student;
- to meet the social demand of the society [4, 35].

It is necessary to mention that the new information technology tools, according to their didactic characteristics, actively influence all components of the educational system: the goal, content, style and organizational forms of teaching, and the development of a person, his intellectual, creative potential, analytical and critical thinking, which is a very complex and urgent issue of pedagogy, independence in the acquisition of knowledge, independence in working with various sources of information, allows to raise and solve the issue of development [5, 3-4].

If we stop at one e-mail (E-mail). Email is an information technology tool that facilitates remote communication. It is one of the services (states) of computer networks. E-mail allows users, teachers and students, to exchange textual and graphic information. To implement the e-mail service, the user's workplace must be equipped with hardware: computer, printer, modem, monitor, keyboard, manipulator mouse and appropriate software.

The didactic features of computer networks can be summarized in the following possibilities of e-mail: transmission of data prepared directly using the computer keyboard or previously saved in the form of files and computer programs; storage of educational information in computer memory with the possibility of printing on a printer; displaying text and graphics on a computer screen; edit incoming text data; preparing and editing the textual information being sent; sending and using computer training programs.

From a didactic point of view, e-mail can be used to create so-called "virtual classrooms". For example, the use of "mailing lists" on the Internet allows a group of users to share ideas together. The number of discussion groups can be very large and is limited by the capabilities of the devices. The rules and methods of subscription (membership) are explained in the created study group, the message sent to the discussion group by a voluntary participant is automatically sent to all participants. One of the participants is a teacher.

Thus, in order to use e-mail, it is necessary to work with a simple text editor and to know a few commands for sending.

In conclusion, one of the main directions of the process of informatization of the current society is the informatization of education. Informatization of education in a broad sense is considered as providing the field of education with methodology, the practice of effective use and

creation (processing) of new information technology tools aimed at the psychological-pedagogical implementation of educational goals.

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